

**glycan
trigger**

D5.1 - Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1

WP5

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CD	Crohn's disease
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
DOI	Digital object identifier
EC	European Commission
EER	Expected exploitable results
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GI	Gastrointestinal
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IBD	Inflammatory bowel disease
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MO	Main objective
R&D	Research and Development
RIA	Research and Innovation Actions
TRL	Technology readiness level
SO	Specific objective
WP	Work Package

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About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health to chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and life-style to maintain a healthy gut. Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

Partners:

I3S (Coordinator)	I3S - INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (Portugal)
LUMC	ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN (The Netherlands)
SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ (France)
CHARITE	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETSMEDIZIN BERLIN (Germany)
GLSMED LH	GLSMED LEARNING HEALTH SA (Portugal)
MOUNT SINAI	ICAHN SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AT MOUNT SINAI (USA)
EFCCA	EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF CROHN'S AND ULCERATIVE COLITIS ASSOCIATIONS (Belgium)
SPI	SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACÃO CONSULTADORIA EMPRESARIAL E FOMENTO DA INOVACÃO SA (Portugal)
LUD	LUDGER LIMITED (United Kingdom)

Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.1 corresponds to the Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1 of the GlycanTrigger project and is developed under the framework of Work Package (WP) 5 “Dissemination, exploitation and communication”. Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI) is the main responsible for this deliverable and the implementation of the strategy and will be supported by core contributions from Institute for Research and Innovation in Health of the University of Porto (i3S), and European Federation of Crohn's and Ulcerative Colitis Associations (EFCCA), among joint efforts from all consortium partners. The purpose of this document is to outline the strategies for communication and dissemination, including their main objectives and approach, target groups, key messages and key performance indicators (KPIs), to ensure that the outreach efforts are effective and aligned with the GlycanTrigger objectives. The exploitation strategy to be followed during and beyond the project lifetime is also presented.

The Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1 will serve as the basis for digital and in person outreach activities, which will be led through a co-creation and patient-centred lens whenever possible in order to foster health self-management and reduce health inequalities, educate citizens on health literacy throughout their lives, and to disseminate knowledge-based chronic disease personalised prevention measures.

The Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan will evolve according to the project context and needs and will be revised in Deliverable D5.2 “Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 2”, due on the 31st of December, 2024.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

The Deliverable “**5.1 - Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1**” is developed under work package 5 (WP5) “Dissemination, exploitation and communication”. The specific objectives of WP5 include: (a) to design and implement a dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy; (b) to develop a clear identity for GlycanTrigger; (c) to map all relevant stakeholders and plan their engagement taking into account their needs, interests and expertise in the GlycanTrigger field of research; (d) to implement a patient-centred co-design approach for transformative change; and (e) to ensure that the results of the project are exploited and have a lasting impact in Europe and the World.

This deliverable is intended to define the communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) strategy, which will contribute to raising awareness about the progress, activities, publications, and events carried out under GlycanTrigger project. The document defines a set of tools and activities to ensure the outreach and visibility during and after the lifespan of the project, through guiding the partners in the clear dissemination and effective exploitation of results in order to create real impact far beyond the conclusion of the project. The plan presented herein includes the overall communication and dissemination strategy, objectives, target audiences, communication and dissemination materials, tools and channels, as well as key performance indicators (KPIs). Moreover, the exploitation strategy proposes a set of measures for knowledge valorisation toward ensuring that non-confidential results are shared with proper audiences and stakeholders, ultimately contributing to the take up of GlycanTrigger’s results for commercial, research, and medical purposes.

In this context, it is relevant to clarify the terms “Communication”, “Dissemination” and “Exploitation”, which lay the foundation for the strategy presented herein. Definitions are provided in [Table 1](#) based on the Horizon Europe Glossary¹.

¹ “Horizon Europe Glossary: a simple guidance through HEU terminology”. Available at: <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-04/HE%20Glossary%20Bridge2HE.pdf>

Table 1. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation definitions

Concept	Definition
Communication	Measures for promoting the project itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The communication activities must be planned and implemented from the outset and continue throughout the entire action. A communication plan must define clear objectives (adapted to various relevant target audiences) and sets out a concrete planning for the communication activities including a description and timing for each activity.
Dissemination	Public disclosure of the results by appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium; in every Horizon Europe work plan a dissemination plan should be included to ensure the sharing of the knowledge produced.
Exploitation	Use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including inter alia, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. It is strongly advised to include such plans in a R&I proposal, especially when the project outputs have a good potential of entering the market.

This document shall be updated throughout the project lifetime, reflecting the evolving nature of a research project and its context. As the project team gains new insights into its target audiences and adjusts its activities to address any gaps or emerging opportunities, the CDE strategy will be revised and refined accordingly. This iterative process will ensure that the plan remains relevant and effective, and that it continues to support the project's objectives and expected impacts.

Chapter 2

GlycanTrigger Communication Strategy

2. GlycanTrigger Communication Strategy

This section presents the GlycanTrigger communication processes, guidelines, and strategies to be followed by all the project partners. The project will follow these guidelines for all its communication activities:

- **Engaging relevant stakeholders early** in the research and innovation process and consistently throughout the project;
- **Avoid a one-size-fits-all kind of approach**, and instead draw on stakeholders' interests;
- **Adapting contents and means to the corresponding target groups**, in order to ensure that clear messages are targeted to specific stakeholders and audiences (including translations, whenever necessary);
- **Continuously monitor, evaluate, and update the communication strategy**, according to project progress and outreach performance.

SPI will be the main responsible for the implementation of the communication strategy. The consortium partners will contribute to make the project visible and to disseminate their own work amongst target audiences (e.g., through social media sharing, and offline initiatives such as meetings or events). Each partner will contribute and suggest internal and external events, publication sites, interactions with stakeholders and provide feedback on the project's communication activities.

To define the GlycanTrigger communication strategy more clearly, the following questions will be addressed:

- Why** do we communicate – goals;
- Who** are we communicating to – target groups;
- What** needs to be communicated – key messages;
- Where** and how to communicate – tools and channels;
- When** will communication take place – action plan

As part of the communication strategy, the deliverable includes the project branding, which will be used as a harmonised visual identity of GlycanTrigger throughout all activities and outreach actions.

2.1 Why do we communicate?

The main goal of GlycanTrigger communication strategy is to make the project visible and increase awareness about the challenges it addresses and its proposed solutions. It envisions active stakeholder

engagement across the different target groups. In order to achieve this, specific objectives (SO) of communication are defined as follows:

- **SO1:** Make GlycanTrigger project, its activities and results visible amongst the target audiences;
- **SO2:** Raise awareness and provide information about chronic inflammatory diseases affecting the gastrointestinal (GI) tract and their impact on patients' quality of life, as well as on research about disease mechanisms such as mucosa glycome and how it impacts on microbiome and gut mucosa immune response, as well as innovative solutions developed under GlycanTrigger;
- **SO3:** Stimulate the involvement of relevant stakeholders in project activities to ensure that the knowledge and solutions generated have a maximum impact by reaching the right audiences;
- **SO4:** Keep stakeholders informed, up-to-date and sustain their interest in the progress of GlycanTrigger and IBDs-related research;
- **SO5:** Promote stakeholder and public engagement in project activities through various communication channels such as social media, newsletters, podcasts and other outreach actions.

2.2 Who are we communicating to?

By defining the target groups, it becomes possible to identify their primary interests and benefits in engaging with the GlycanTrigger project, as well as their significance to the project and consortium. This enables better definition of key messages, requirements for message adaptation (language), and the most effective channels and tools for reaching these audiences. Considering GlycanTrigger context, motivation, activities and communication objectives, the target groups to engage through different tools during project implementation are detailed in [Table 2](#).

Table 2. Description of GlycanTrigger communication target groups

Target audience	Description	Interests
Medical healthcare community and	This group includes specialised professionals with a high level of knowledge and technical understanding in the disciplines covered by the project, namely medical doctors, hospital and clinics' staff, healthcare professionals, nutritionists and possibly psychologists. This group is believed to be interested in the GlycanTrigger outputs.	This group will have an interest in the knowledge resulting from GlycanTrigger and in participating in discussions regarding the receipt/provision of health counselling, as well as in establishing personalised prevention measures for chronic diseases. This group will be able to provide the most informed advice and clinical decisions, ensuring patients' best interests. This group is highly relevant for the dissemination and exploitation strategy as well.
Scientific technology community and	This group includes specialised professionals with a high level of knowledge and technical understanding in the disciplines covered by the project. It covers higher education institutions, research and technology organisations, chronic disease research networks (e.g.,	This group will be interested in learning about IBDs-related diseases and in understanding the direction and progress of the field. They can provide valuable insights and expertise on the subject. The technology community could play an important role in advancing the field of glycomics and -omics, and glycoengineering, which involves the modification of glycans for therapeutic or diagnostic purposes.

Target audience	Description	Interests
	European Crohn's and Colitis Organization-ECCO).	This group is highly relevant for the dissemination and exploitation strategy as well.
Other EU projects and initiatives	This group corresponds to the international networks brought together under EU projects working within the same thematic, as well as research and innovation networks. The group will be relevant to establish joint communication actions.	This group will share research interests with GlycanTrigger and will be interested in creating momentum on personalised prevention for IBDs and health literacy awareness.
Policymakers, institutions and authorities	EU and This group includes individuals that are often referred to as specialists from governmental, intergovernmental and regulatory bodies. It includes national and European health policy makers, but also key opinion leaders and regulators (e.g., European Food Safety Authority).	This group is interested in making informed decisions and negotiations, supported by scientifically and clinically accurate data. This group is highly relevant for the dissemination and exploitation strategy as well.
Industry representatives	This group includes pharma, nutraceutical companies, and food companies. The group includes also representatives of the innovative industry, covering specialists and venture capitalists, as well as other roles from technical to managerial.	This group is interested in guaranteeing the future technological transfer of the results of GlycanTrigger into a commercial product for chronic inflammation prevention. They will be most keen on understanding the impact of the new findings for chronic diseases as well as on the development of a new pre-biotic/nutritional supplement plausible to be used as a preventive strategy. This group is highly relevant for the dissemination and exploitation strategy as well.
Patients' associations and medical associations	and This group includes non-profit organisations that represent the interests of patients and healthcare professionals, respectively.	This group will have interest in the knowledge resulting from GlycanTrigger, and in participating in discussions regarding the current treatment/prevention options.
Patients and their families	This group includes IBD-diagnosed patients, their families and at-risk relatives, and other informal caregivers.	This group will be interested in learning more about chronic inflammatory diseases in GI tract, organisations or institutions working with these diseases, networking with other patients and families, etc. They will also be interested in understanding the disease mechanisms and its relation to the increased risk of other chronic diseases.
Civil Society	This group includes civil society in general, i.e., citizens with supposedly limited or general previous knowledge about IBDs-related diseases.	This group can benefit from GlycanTrigger as they may become patients themselves, and will therefore have a source of rigorous and curated information about chronic inflammatory diseases in GI tract, being empowered to take preventive actions.
Media	This group includes science journalists, mass media, online news outlets.	This group will be interested in conveying innovate, ground-breaking and "fresh" messages about developments in the field and their impact.

2.3 What to communicate?

GlycanTigger aims to understand the communication needs of each stakeholder in order to ensure they are involved and engaged in the project. Key messages of the project were defined and categorised in four main themes and definitions.

- **GlycanTrigger general key messages:**
 - **To make GlycanTrigger visible by communicating project activities**, such as consortium meetings, thematic workshops, webinars, participation in national and international conferences, news in external media platforms, etc., as well as project results and achievements;
 - **To stimulate stakeholder engagement by developing targeted content and actions**, such as communication materials, social media campaigns, outreach actions, etc.
- **GlycanTrigger specific key messages:**
 - **To raise awareness regarding chronic Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBDs)**, more specifically Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC); inform what are the current means for prevention, diagnosis, and treatment; and how these diseases can affect diagnosed and undiagnosed patients and their families;
 - **To provide information to patients and the general public** regarding each specific IBD condition, including their causes, genetic and environmental risk factors, preventive care strategies, support platforms and services;
 - **To promote a health literacy** through better-informed management of health status, diet and lifestyle to maintain a healthy gut as a preventive behaviour;
 - **To inform patients and their families about organisations working on IBDs** and their activities at the national level and European level;
 - **To foster collaboration, networking and outreach** between IBDs and IBDs-related NGOs, medical associations, sister projects and topic-related initiatives

Further specific key messages will be identified with consortium partners representing different stakeholder types. Messages will be updated as the project evolves and further defined in the upcoming versions of the present deliverable.

2.4 Where and how do we communicate?

This section describes the tools, channels and activities that will be used by GlycanTrigger partners for external communication, i.e., to convey the messages about the project, its progress and related topics to the abovementioned audiences in the most effective manner. GlycanTrigger will create and maintain its own channels, which will be detailed in the following sections, but will also leverage the partners networks toward increased reach. **Table 3** summarises the communication tools and channels that are already in place or soon to be developed/implemented during the project's lifetime. Currently existing channels are further detailed below.

Table 3. GlycanTrigger communication channels and activities

Tools & Channels	Purpose	Target Audiences
Project branding	Unique visual identity in all project materials to improve brand recognition (including logo, documentation and presentation templates)	All target groups
Project website	Main hub of information about the project (activities, progress, news, publications and educational materials). It includes links to partners' websites	
Press release	Issued for specific GlycanTrigger activities, achievements and for dissemination of the project's impact	
Visual communication materials	Project brochures, infographics, videos, and best practice materials in digital and/or physical formats	
Social media	Accounts on LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram for the dissemination of IBD educational digital materials and patient-centred awareness campaigns, surveys/questionnaires, as well as major research outputs of GlycanTrigger.	Medical and healthcare community; scientific and technology community; patients' associations and medical associations; patients and their families; civil society
E-newsletter	Quarterly e-newsletter providing information on GlycanTrigger's progress, IBD educational content, and patient surveys. A downloadable version will be available on the project website	
Podcast	12 episodes containing expert interviews and dissemination of tools for patients	
Videos	One main video, and teaser videos detailing the main activities and achievements of the project	Medical and healthcare community; scientific and technology community; policymakers, EU institutions and authorities; patients' associations and medical associations; patients and their families; media

2.4.1 Website

The GlycanTrigger website (www.glycantrigger.eu) is a project deliverable (**D5.6 – Project Website**) and will be launched in April 2023 (M4). It will act as the central communication channel aimed at academia, researchers, public and private sectors, policymakers, and professionals. The website will:

- **Present the project**, including information about GlycanTrigger, its goals and mission, the consortium and all involved teams;
- **Provide information about IBDs**, including the specific conditions onto which the project focuses, and useful links for patients, families and the general public;
- **Promote project results**, including events and activities, scientific and medical publications, infographics, factsheets, relevant materials for partners and stakeholders, etc;
- **Merge and market other communication channels and tools**, including social media (feed), press releases, external events, and newsletters.

Moreover, it will contain essential aspects such as the EU emblem, funding acknowledgement, disclaimer, privacy policy, contacts, and social media handles. In regard to maintenance, the website will be continuously updated by SPI, in line with the developments associated with the progress of project activities.

2.4.2 Social media channels

Engagement through appropriate social media platforms is an effective way for targeted outreach and for fostering two-way communication. LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram were selected as the social media channels to be used to disseminate information, publications, and events from the project. Hence, the project was kick-started by creating the following communication channels, as shown in **Figure 1**:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/glycantrigger-eu-project/>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/GlycanTrigger>
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/glycantrigger_project/

All social media platforms will be managed by the SPI team. A social media strategy will be implemented to ensure the messaging and content fit the social media platform selected and its target audience.

Figure 1. GlycanTrigger social media profiles – LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram

The writing style used in GlycanTrigger communication activities should be informal and non-technical. Some keywords/ hashtags will be used on social media publications to increase the project's visibility, such as:

[#GlycanTrigger](#) [#HorizonEU](#) [#EU](#) [#Europe](#) [#HorizonEurope](#) [#CrohnsDisease](#) [#UlcerativeColitis](#)
[#InflammatoryBowelDisease](#) [#Glycans](#) [#glycotime](#) [#Prevention](#)

In addition, relevant profiles of partners and stakeholders will be tagged in publications through their respective organisational accounts for enhancing the overall effectiveness of communication. The project will also link with the European Commission (EC) social media, as a means to integrate the community of Horizon Europe projects: [@HorizonEU](#), [@EU_Commission](#), [@EU_HaDEA](#)

A table available to all partners with information on tags and rules for publication/dissemination will be provided.

2.4.3 Press releases

Press releases will be developed and shared through lead channels of the project. Such communication statements will focus on specific achievements of the project and will be used to communicate the progress of the project in a non-technical format targeting both specialists and non-specialist audiences. For a wider reach, press releases could be translated to the native languages of the publishing partners. The first press release was published on March 10th, 2023, to announce the official kick-off meeting of the project (**Figure 2**). It was published in English and Portuguese.

GlycanTrigger - Glycans as master triggers of health to intestinal inflammation transition

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the **Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions**, that addresses how changes in the composition of glycans (sugar-chains) exposed at the surface of the gut mucosa (the gut glycome), act as a primary event that dysregulates local and systemic mechanisms leading to inflammation. The team is studying how those changes can start a chain reaction that leads to intestinal inflammation. GlycanTrigger is exploring the novel concept of “glycan mimicry”, i.e., the idea that some molecules can imitate or resemble the sugar code (the glycome) found in our body and trick our immune system, ultimately causing inflammation in the digestive system.

Inflammatory bowel diseases include two **idiopathic** and **incurable** diseases – **Crohn’s disease** and **ulcerative colitis** – characterized by an uncontrolled inflammation of the digestive tract. GlycanTrigger is testing an **innovative hypothesis** in which changes in the glycome composition in the gut lead to imbalances in bacteria composition (the microbiome) and in gut immunity which ultimately cause a shift from health to inflammation. The project aims at understanding whether this glycan-shift could be an early event that triggers inflammation in inflammatory bowel diseases. Additionally, it envisions a new strategy for predicting and preventing **inflammatory bowel diseases**.

GlycanTrigger will last 6 years and brings together **9 partners from 7 different EU and non-EU countries**. The project started in January 2023 and is **coordinated by i3S** - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Portugal.

The official **kick-off meeting** of the GlycanTrigger project will be a **1.5-day event** held in **Porto** (Portugal) on **March 13th and 14th**. The aim of the meeting is to lay the foundations for the GlycanTrigger project, in order to get the project off the ground and officially get started on the proceedings for the implementation of the activities planned.

GlycanTrigger Partners:

- Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde (**i3S**), Portugal
- Leiden University Medical Center (**LUMC**), the Netherlands
- Sorbonne University, France
- Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany
- GLSMED Learning Health (**GLSMED LH**), Portugal
- Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai, USA
- European Federation of Crohn’s & Ulcerative Colitis Associations (**EFCCA**), Belgium
- Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (**SPI**), Portugal
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Figure 2. English version of GlycanTrigger’s first press release

2.4.4 Visual communication materials

Visual communication materials will be developed as effective tools to communicate with the target audience, in a way that is accessible and engaging. This will include infographics, brochures and other visual aids, as described above. In addition, a flyer has been developed to introduce GlycanTrigger social

media channels to project partners, which was distributed during the kick-off meeting of the project (Figure 3). Additional materials will be developed throughout the project and provided in the updates of this plan.

Figure 3. GlycanTrigger's first flyer

2.4.5 E-newsletter

A digital newsletter (e-newsletter) will be a useful tool to inform target audiences and stakeholders about the progress of the GlycanTrigger project. It will provide subscribers with regular updates on the latest developments and upcoming activities of the project. Every four months (Table 4), starting June 2023, a newsletter will be published in the project website and social media, as well as distributed via email to the consortium members and target audiences who have subscribed. Newsletters will be short and flexible in structure, comprising key messages in 1-2 pages and including links for more detailed information, whenever suitable.

Table 4. GlycanTrigger newsletter release plan

Volume	Tentative Release Month	Tentative Content
1	June 2023 (M6)	Presentation of GlycanTrigger: aims, consortium, communication channels (website, social media channels), news and upcoming events
2	October 2023 (M10)	Project updates, including progress made in the first months, and upcoming events
3	February 2024 (M14)	Summary of the Year 1: results, publications, activities, news, upcoming events, etc.
4	June 2024 (M18)	Featured research or innovations related to the project, updates from project partners, and upcoming events
5	October 2024 (M22)	Project updates, milestones achieved, news, upcoming events, etc.
6	February 2025 (M26)	Summary of the Year 2: results, publications, activities, news, upcoming events, etc.
7	June 2025 (M30)	Partner updates and collaborations, and upcoming events
8	October 2025 (M34)	Featured research or innovations related to the project updates from project partners, and upcoming events

Volume	Tentative Release Month	Tentative Content
9	February 2026 (M38)	Summary of the Year 3: results, publications, activities, news, upcoming events, etc.
10	June 2026 (M42)	Highlight of outreach and engagement efforts, such as public events or social media campaigns
11	October 2026 (M46)	Interviews or Q&A sessions with project partners, stakeholders, or experts in the field
12	February 2027 (M50)	Summary of the Year 4: results, publications, activities, news, events, etc.
13	June 2027 (M54)	Featured research or innovations related to the project updates from project partners, and upcoming events
14	October 2027 (M58)	Project updates, milestones achieved, news, upcoming events, etc.
15	February 2028 (M62)	Summary of the Year 5: results, publications, activities, news, events, etc.
16	June 2028 (M66)	Final project updates and achievements, and plans for the future
17	October 2028 (M70)	Final summary of GlycanTrigger: relevant results, outcomes and impacts

A schedule for partners' contribution in each number will be provided.

2.4.6 Podcast/Videos

Twelve podcast episodes will be released during the lifetime of the GlycanTrigger project, with two episodes per year. These will be short interviews with experts on chronic inflammatory diseases in GI tract talking about their work and challenges. It can include doctors, researchers, patient advocates, among others. The podcasts will be available on Youtube, and published on the website and social media channels. As part of this effort, the project coordinator (Salomé Pinho) participated in the podcast series "GlycanHub Podcast" discussing the relation between glycans and the immune system ([Figure 4](#)). Other project videos detailing the main activities and achievements of the project will be also developed.

Figure 4. Podcast episode featuring the GlycanTrigger project coordinator

2.5 When to communicate?

The GlycanTrigger action plan for the communication strategy is presented in [Table 5](#) and will be generally defined by three major phases:

- **Phase 1 (M1-M5):** in this initial phase, the main communication strategy will be designed, including the project identity, a general understanding of the necessary approach for the project (driving objectives for communication and approach to stakeholders), initial stakeholder mapping and implementation of part of the communication channels (website and social media platforms).
- **Phase 2 (M6-M17):** this phase will be focused on the initial steps to raise awareness, launching other communication tools and channels (e.g., newsletter and press releases), updating communication ideas and strategy.
- **Phase 3 (M18-M72):** encouraging community engagement online and offline, with continuous update of the communication strategy considering performance reports.

Table 5. Timeline of GlycanTrigger communication activities

Communication Actions	Year 1												Year 2												Year 3														
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36			
Create visual identity			█																																				
Create social media channels			█																																				
Social media posts			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Website development			█	█																																			
Website update			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Visual communication materials				█								█												█														█	
Newsletter						█				█				█				█				█				█									█				
Press release			█									█						█						█														█	
Podcast & Videos						█						█						█						█														█	
Development of CDE plan and updates					D5.1																			D5.2															

A selection of initiatives (**Table 6**) was made to support the communication action plan, particularly regarding social media posts, as effective stakeholder engagement depends on the timing and consistency of communication. These dates provide opportunities to produce and release content that can have maximum impact.

Table 6. Relevant dates for GlycanTrigger communication activities

February	
11	International Day of Women in Science
March	
8	International Women's Day
April	
7	World Health Day
May	
19	World IBD Day
29	World Digestive Health Day
June	
27	World Gut Microbiome Day
August	
Month	Gastroparesis Awareness Month
December	
1	World Crohn's and Colitis Day

2.6 Monitoring

The primary goal of monitoring is to make sure that the communication plan is well executed. It is crucial to conduct regular monitoring of the project's communication efforts because their impact is key to the successful project implementation. To ensure accurate impact assessment, the quality of implementation, and, when needed, updates or adjustments of communication activities, this evaluation will be done continuously. Monitoring can be broken down into sub-sections:

- Performance measurement;
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs);
- Reporting.

2.6.1 Performance Measurement

The implementation of this plan will be continuously measured according to the pace of the technical execution of the project and in articulation with GlycanTrigger stakeholders and target audience. Specific KPIs have been defined and are presented in the following section. This information will be gathered by SPI and shared with the project partners every 6 months. Performance measurement involves the following steps:

- **Analysis and interpretation:** Once the data has been collected, it must be analysed and interpreted in order to understand what it means for the communication activities. This can involve identifying trends, strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for improvement.
- **Action plan:** Based on the analysis and interpretation, an action plan may need to be developed to improve communication activities. This can involve adjusting messaging, targeting, channels, or tactics.
- **Review and refinement:** Finally, regular reviews are needed and refinement of the communication plan will ensure that it remains effective and aligned with communication goals and objectives and that it supports project impacts. This can involve revisiting KPIs, data collection methods, reporting frequency, analysis, and action plan.

2.6.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs enable the quantitative assessment of performance by setting target values for communication goals.

Table 7 presents KPIs for GlycanTrigger communication activities and the means for their verification.

Table 7. KPIs of GlycanTrigger communication strategy

Tools & Channels	KPIs	Means of verification
Project website	No. of visitors per year: 1700 visitors with at least 2 minutes/visit	Google analytics
Social media	Total no. of followers and no. of posts per year: 1,000 followers (total) and 15 posts/year	Social media analytics
Press releases	No. of press releases: At least 2 press releases/year	Project reporting, website analytics
Visual communication materials	No. of infographics developed and no. of downloads: 800 printed brochures/flyers and 500 downloads	Project reporting, Website analytics
E-newsletter	No. of newsletters and no. of subscribers: 3 newsletters per year and at least 250 subscribers	Platform analytics
Podcast	No. of podcast listeners: At least 80 listeners/podcast episode	Platform analytics
Videos	No. of videos produced and no. of views: 3 videos and at least 150 views/video/year	Platform analytics

These numbers may be adjusted according with the pace of the technical execution of the project.

2.6.3 Reporting

GlycanTrigger partners will be asked to provide internal communication reports every 6 months, in order to allow SPI to keep track of the progress reached by the consortium against the objectives and the targets set in this Communication Plan. **Table 8** provides a summary of the reporting plan.

Table 8. Reporting plan for GlycanTrigger communication activities

Reporting no.	Month	Communication activities reporting period
1	June 2023 (M6)	01/01/2023 to 30/06/2023
2	December 2023 (M12)	01/07/2023 to 31/12/2023
3	June 2024 (M18)	01/01/2024 to 30/06/2024
4	December 2024 (M24)	01/07/2024 to 31/12/2024
5	June 2025 (M30)	01/01/2025 to 30/06/2025
6	December 2025 (M36)	01/07/2025 to 31/12/2025
7	June 2026 (M42)	01/01/2026 to 30/06/2026
8	December 2026 (M48)	01/07/2026 to 31/12/2026
9	June 2027 (M54)	01/01/2027 to 30/06/2027
10	December 2027 (M60)	01/07/2027 to 31/12/2027
11	June 2028 (M66)	01/01/2028 to 30/06/2028
12	December 2028 (M72)	01/07/2028 to 31/12/2028

Dedicated reporting templates and other documents/evidences will be made available online on the collaborative space. In addition, narrative reports will be requested to project partners that organise GlycanTrigger workshops and events.

2.7 Visual identity

As a first step to kick-start the activities of external communication, a visual identity was established in order to make the project easily identifiable and to standardise the visual elements. The branding pack, that was prepared by SPI and should be used by all project members, includes a project logo, colour palette and a series of Microsoft Word and PowerPoint templates, to be used during all communication and dissemination activities.

2.7.1 Project logo and colour palette

The logo of a project is a powerful tool that can create engagement by distinguishing it from others and facilitating its recognition. As it represents one of the initial impressions that reaches the target audience, it should be thoughtfully crafted. The logo must effectively communicate the essence of the project while the colour palette should reinforce the association of all graphical elements with the key concepts of the message. The GlycanTrigger logo (**Figure 5**) is constituted by two main elements: a graphical representation on the left, and the name of the project on the right. The graphic features a representation of the intestine as its centrepiece, as well as a gear-wheel to represent the concept of a "trigger", as it initiates the movement of other gears in a system, representing the mechanisms underlying the health to inflammation transition. At the bottom of the graphical representation, glycan structures are also depicted.

This combination of elements visually represents the focus of the GlycanTrigger project, which seeks to better understand the role of glycans in intestinal health-to-disease transition.

Figure 5. GlycanTrigger logo

The colour palette (**Figure 6**) was selected based on the official colours of the coordinating institution, i3S, which uses shades of blue as its representative colour.

Figure 6. GlycanTrigger colour palette

2.7.2 Documentation Template

A set of graphical templates have been developed in order to ensure a professional level of quality and consistency in terms of design and presentation in all the project documents and communications. The project Word and PowerPoint templates were designed and shared with all the partners. All documents produced such as reports, deliverables (public or confidential) or meeting agendas or minutes, should use the Word template (**Figure 7**). All presentations performed within the Consortium meetings and internal or external activities or events should use the PowerPoint template (**Figure 8**).

Insert document subtitle

Insert document title

Date: xx xx xxxxx
Contact: xx xx xxxxx

DOCUMENT CONTROL SHEET

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Number	101005907
Project Acronym	GlycanTrigger
Project Full title	Glycans as master triggers of health to intestinal inflammation transition
Project Start Date	1 January 2023
Project Duration	72 months
Funding Instrument	Horizon Europe
Funding Scheme	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHEALTH-02-01
Coordinator	Sabine Pirho (IS) sabine@iuh.uu.se

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable No	
Deliverable Title	
Work Package No	
WP Package Title	
WP Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	
Task No	
Task Title	
Task Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	
Task Sponsor (Name and Short Org. Name)	
Other Authors (Name and Short Org. Name)	
Reviewers (Name and Short Org. Name)	
Status	Not Final 0
Deliverable Type	Report (D) Demonstration (D) Other (0)
Dissemination Level	Public (P) Restricted (R) Confidential (C)

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DOCUMENT VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change

DOCUMENT REVIEW

Reviewer	Date	Reviewer Name (Short Organisation Name)

Legal disclaimer

This project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101005907. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition

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Chapter number

Chapter Subtitle

2. Title 1

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing

2.1 Title 2

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting.

Title

Figure 1. Insert figure caption here.

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting.

Table 1. Insert table title here.

Lorem ipsum				
Lorem ipsum				
Lorem ipsum				
Lorem ipsum				
Lorem ipsum				

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2.1.1 Title 2

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book:

RGB	RGB	RGB	RGB
36	0	212	234
95	186	269	234
204	223	247	234

Figure 2. Insert figure caption here.

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Figure 7. Project documentation template – Word

The figure displays six PowerPoint slide templates for the 'glycan trigger' project, arranged in a 3x2 grid. Each slide includes the 'glycan trigger' logo and 'Funded by the European Union' logo.

- Slide 1 (Top Left):** Title slide. Features the glycan trigger logo, a subtitle placeholder 'ADD SUBTITLE HERE', a title placeholder 'ADD TITLE HERE', and a code 'DDMMYYYY'.
- Slide 2 (Top Right):** Table of Contents. Lists four chapters with placeholder titles and descriptions.
- Slide 3 (Middle Left):** Chapter 1 content. Includes a title box '1 Chapter title', a description box 'Here describe the topic of the chapter', and a large text area with placeholder text.
- Slide 4 (Middle Right):** Chapter 5 content. Includes a title box '5. Insert title', a text area 'Click to add text', and a table with five columns and three rows of placeholder text.
- Slide 5 (Bottom Left):** Chapter 6 content. Includes a title box '6. Insert title', a text area 'Click to add text', and a bar chart with four categories and three series.
- Slide 6 (Bottom Right):** Footer slide. Features the glycan trigger logo, website URL 'Website: www.xxxx.xx', social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook, and the EU funding logo.

Figure 8. Project documentation template – Power Point

2.7.3 Social media publications templates

For the social media channels, a set of templates have been developed in order to define a visual identity for the publications. Four different types of templates (Figure 9) were created: (i, ii) an informative template for educational posts, (iii) an event announcement template, (iv) a podcast episode template, (v) a partners' information template, and (vi) a scientific publication template. The informative publications should aim to answer standard questions in order to create awareness and health literacy about chronic inflammatory disease in GI tract. The event announcement template should contain general information about the event, such as the date and location (if it is a public event), the goals of the event and an allusive photo. The podcast template serves to inform about the release of a new episode containing information on the topic covered and the invited interviewee. The partners' information template must contain the partners' logo,

brief partners' information and their contributions to the project. The scientific publication template will be used to share new scientific work and must contain the title of the publication, the authors and the digital object identifier (DOI).

Figure 9. Social media publications templates

2.7.4 Funding Statement

As part of the official guidelines from the European Commission for Horizon Europe, “Beneficiaries of EU funding must display the EU flag and funding statement (“Funded by the European Union”) in all their communication and dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results funded by the grant.” Whenever relevant, the following funding acknowledgement can be used: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101093997”.

For any publication, the following disclaimer must be added: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or The Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Figure 10. EU funding acknowledgement emblem

The funding statement must include the EU emblem (**Figure 10**), which must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

2.7.5 European general data protection regulation (GDPR)

The GlycanTrigger's consortium is committed to protecting privacy rights, including personal data (information that relates to an individual who can be directly or indirectly identified), in full conformity with the new European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as well as other relevant directives such as Directive 2002/58/EC concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications)². The consortium is committed to complying with those obligations with care and with a proactive approach.

IP addresses should be considered as personal data as the text includes "online identifier", in the definition of "personal data". Tracking the IPs of website visitors without their consent in Europe could lead to legal consequences under the rules of GDPR. The consortium is committed to complying with those obligations, legal requirements, and consequences, with a proactive approach. The following GDPR issues must be considered:

- **Website visitor tracking:** In order to optimize the user experience on GlycanTrigger's website, information such as name, email, IP address, date and location of access may be collected when users allow cookies on their browsers.
- **Events:** Personal information is collected through registration, such as Name; Position; Email; Interests. Communications may also be sent by email to event attendees, who give their consent to this treatment. These attendees may request the removal of their information from the communication listings by sending the request to GlycanTrigger e-mail address at glycantrigger@gmail.com.

² "What is GDPR, the EU's new data protection law?" Available on: <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>

Chapter 3

GlycanTrigger Dissemination Strategy

3. GlycanTrigger Dissemination Strategy

The main objective of dissemination is to reveal and advance the outcomes of a project to enable others to utilise them, expanding the project's impact beyond its duration, and dissemination activities should start once project results are available. Dissemination aims to encourage the sharing of knowledge with relevant communities and stakeholders, promoting engagement and sustainability of the project. It is equally essential to accurately recognise the intended audience and the dissemination channels. The plan for dissemination should be supervised and revised as appropriate, with all partners contributing their endeavours to guarantee its successful execution.

3.1 Dissemination objectives

The GlycanTrigger dissemination strategy has 2 main objectives (MO), which are further subdivided into specific objectives (SO):

- **MO1: Raise awareness and maximize impact by openly sharing knowledge**
 - **SO1.1:** Openly and transparently sharing knowledge, in a free-of-charge way (open sciences) without compromising intellectual property rights (IPR);
 - **SO1.2:** Support decision and policy-making by the different players in the field of IBDs-related diseases, health, and politics, by providing access to project results by clinical teams, health management structures, policymakers that will assist the delineation of guidelines for IBDs pathways of treatment/prevention;
 - **SO1.3:** Inform about the efforts of GlycanTrigger to address IBDs-related diseases, and how patients and their families, among other target groups, can benefit from project outcomes;
 - **SO1.4:** Educate the public about IBDs to improve health literacy and help dispel misconceptions about IBDs-related diseases, contributing to patient's empowerment towards disease prevention.
- **MO2: Support engagement with stakeholders at the national, European and international levels**
 - **SO2.1:** Engage with potential early adopters or end-users of project results, understanding their needs and interests, paving the way to produce robust value propositions of project results and outcomes (supportive role of exploitation);
 - **SO2.2:** Pave the way for future collaborations with research, clinical, pharma/food industry or policy-making partners, by facilitating networking between the consortium and external partners with synergistic interests.

3.2 Dissemination target groups

Target groups and their objectives are identified in [Table 9](#).

Table 9. Overview of GlycanTrigger dissemination target groups and objectives

Target Groups	Objectives
Medical and healthcare community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To foster personalised prevention and personalised early diagnosis tools for IBD
Scientific and technology community; other EU projects and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To disseminate main conclusions amongst the R&D community, to enable the scientific community to leverage the results that are developed To foster new international collaborations toward maximising research impact
Policymakers, EU institutions and authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To consult and disseminate transformative personalised prevention measures and treatment solutions for IBD
Industry representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To disseminate new developments and promote the continuum of the innovation path of GlycanTrigger, envisioning the development of a new pre-biotic/nutritional supplement plausible to be used as a preventive strategy
Patients' associations and medical associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To provide research findings and policy developments to potential stakeholders
Patients and their families; civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To ensure horizontal knowledge dissemination and engage civil society, especially patients and their families, to promote patient empowerment and self-health management

3.3 Dissemination tools and channels

After identifying the target groups, it is necessary to understand how these audiences can be effectively reached and engaged for dissemination purposes. In this section, the main dissemination channels and tools are presented in [Table 10](#).

Table 10. Dissemination channels and tools

Channels & tools	Main objectives
Project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Be a central element for an active dissemination strategy, highlighting project results and outcomes; Be a hub of information for patients and other relevant stakeholders.
Social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advertise progress, results and other dissemination activities to targeted audiences.
Scientific publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform the scientific community on the results and outcomes of GlycanTrigger; Create opportunity for future collaborations.
Thematic webinars and workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve patient outcomes and empower individuals affected by IBDs-related diseases through education, support, and guidance, as well as gathering input and co-creating patient empowerment guidelines.
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raise awareness about IBDs prevention through a patient-centred training program

Channels & tools	Main objectives
Internal and external events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of results through lectures, speaking engagements, conferences, and interviews; Present key findings and conclusions of the project, increase awareness of IBDs-related diseases, and promote collaboration opportunities with relevant stakeholders.
Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform about GlycanTrigger progress, results, outcomes, activities and events.

It is also convenient to understand how all the different channels reach specific target groups (**Table 11**), as this will ensure the correct adjustment of messaging (language) and selection of the key messages to be delivered, according to the target group to be reached.

Table 11. Groups targeted by each dissemination channel and tools

Target groups	Medical and healthcare community	Scientific and technology community; other EU projects and initiatives	Policymakers, EU institutions and authorities	Industry representatives	Patients' associations and medical associations	Patients and their families; civil society
Project website	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media	X	X	X	X	X	X
Scientific publications	X	X	X	X	X	
Thematic webinars and workshops	X	X	X	X	X	X
Training	X				X	X
Internal and external events	X	X	X	X	X	
Newsletter	X	X	X	X	X	

3.4 Dissemination key messages

The GlycanTrigger dissemination strategy will focus on sharing the project results and outcomes. **Table 12** outlines the key messages that are expected to be disseminated based on the anticipated outcomes of WP1-4, which aim to generate new scientific and clinical knowledge.

Table 12. Main messages to be disseminated per WP

WP1	Outcomes regarding gut mucosa glycome in health-to-inflammation transition
WP2	Outcomes regarding the biological impact of changes in gut glycome in microbial and immunological dynamics
WP3	Outcomes regarding the understanding of the cellular and molecular mechanisms underlying the activation of innate and humoral immune responses by changes in gut glycosylation
WP4	Outcomes regarding therapeutic efficacy of glyco-metabolic remodelling in preventing health-to-inflammation transition

3.5 Open Science

GlycanTrigger will follow open science practices, applying the FAIR data principles, i.e., producing data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

- Persistent identifiers will be assigned to the shared data, so to make data findable;
- Detailed documentation on the datasets will be provided;
- Standardized methodologies will enable data to be interoperable;
- The relevant data collected in the course of the project, except sensitive and personal data, will be made openly available, with respect to possible embargo periods, through data repositories and with suitable licenses, thus making data re-usable.

Outcomes will be published or otherwise disseminated in an appropriate form, although publication or release of findings may be delayed for a reasonable period to allow for protection and commercialization of intellectual property. In this case, publications should be postponed until IP protection has been granted.

Research papers will be published in open-access platforms, becoming available free of cost. Whenever possible, preprint servers (e.g. MedRxiv; BioRxiv) will be used to ensure easy access to the research data, allowing potentially impactful results to be rapidly made available, accelerating further research and applications to clinical practice.

Creative Commons (CC) licenses will be implemented to guide subsequent use of data and other intellectual products, providing robust legal code, while being also free and easily readable by end-users.

The leader of the consortium will monitor the open science practices, recognizing the critical aspect of major importance of our results in low-income countries. All non-confidential results and public project deliverables will be made available to the public through the project website.

3.6 Monitoring

For monitoring all GlycanTrigger dissemination efforts tools and strategies for performance measurement, key performance indicators (KPIs) and reporting are defined herein.

3.6.1 Performance Measurement

Performance measurement of dissemination activities will be done based on KPIs (section 3.6.2) and by the number of successful collaborations extending beyond the project, as long as they have been a result of any dissemination activity.

3.6.2 Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The monitoring of dissemination activities should be done based on KPIs, as defined in the Grant Agreement (GA). For this purpose, target KPIs and means of verification were defined for each dissemination activity and are presented in [Table 13](#).

Table 13. GlycanTrigger dissemination KPIs and means of verification

Tools & Channels	KPIs	Means of verification
Scientific publications	Expected approximately 10 scientific publications	Project reporting, Google scholar
Webinars and workshops	GlycanTrigger Research Webinar Series – 2 per year, 15 participants each GlycanTrigger Joint Workshop Series – 2 per year, 10 participants each GlycanTrigger Online Co-creation Workshops – 1 per year, 10 participants each	Number of participants, project reporting
Q&A sessions	20 participants each	Number of participants, project reporting
Training for Change	Specialised Training for Patients – 20 participants GlycanTrigger Transferability event – 1 event, 20 participants each	Number of participants, project reporting
Third Party events	N/A (Participation of researchers from the consortium to external events)	Number of participants, project reporting
Launch and final events	2 events, 50 participants each	Number of participants, project reporting

3.6.3 Reporting

Similar to communication activities, all partners should inform SPI about the participation or organisation of a dissemination event. The results of the dissemination activities will be collected every 6 months and reported to the partners during a yearly communications meeting with the partners, to review the results and adapt the strategies in place, if needed. Dedicated reporting templates will be made available in the online collaborative space.

Chapter 4

GlycanTrigger Exploitation Strategy

4. GlycanTrigger Exploitation Strategy

The exploitation strategy is positioned at developing a sustainable exit plan to efficiently exploit tangible and intangible project results towards maximising impact. Exploitation will be initiated at the beginning of the project and will extend beyond project lifetime. The GlycanTrigger exploitation strategy will be developed under Task 5.1 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan” and further supported by Task 6.3 “Intellectual property rights (IPR)” in order to ensure the take up of GlycanTrigger’s results for commercial, research, and medical purposes. Overall, the exploitation strategy will ensure that non-confidential knowledge and results are shared with proper audiences and stakeholders, and that Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are identified.

All Horizon Europe beneficiaries are required to use their best efforts in developing exploitation activities to increase the mid- and long-term impact of project outcomes, up to four years after the end of the action. This includes direct exploitation or indirect exploitation by another entity, by transfer or licensing. If such efforts fail, the GA also foresees that *‘if, despite a beneficiary’s best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results. If results are incorporated in a standard, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority or unless it is impossible) ask the standardisation body to include the funding statement (see Article 17) in (information related to) the standard.’*

4.1 Exploitation objectives

The main objectives of the exploitation plan of GlycanTrigger are:

- To effectively **deliver the relevant knowledge, outcomes and results produced to the target groups** identified;
- To **deliver a measurable benefit to society** through the **valorisation of project outcomes** and its **KERs**;
- To contribute to the project’s sustainability in terms of **knowledge transfer** and **replicability beyond the funding period**.

4.2 Key impact pathways (KIPs)

To monitor and increase the impact of EU-funded projects, Horizon Europe relies on the concept of Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) (Table 15) to maximise the insight of stakeholders regarding the benefits and effects of the funded projects in the economy and society. Identifying KIPs will allow the selection of time-sensitive indicators (short, medium and long-term) to support the monitorisation of project’s impact. Such indicators are proposed for each KIP and can be re(de)defined for the specific purposes of the project.

Table 14. Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) in Horizon Europe

Category	Key Impact Pathway
Scientific impact	KIP1. Creating high-quality new knowledge KIP2. Strengthening human capital in research and innovation KIP3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open Source
Societal impact	KIP4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through research and innovation KIP5. Delivering benefits and impact through research and innovation missions KIP6. Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society
Technological/economic impact	KIP7. Generating innovation-based growth KIP8. Creating more and better jobs KIP9. Leveraging investment in research and innovation

Based on GlycanTrigger expected impacts, six main KIPs across the three categories are anticipated to be the most relevant pathways to maximize impact and communicate the value of the project:

- **Scientific impact:** Uptake of new open knowledge on the role of glycans in health-to-inflammation transition and in disease prevention will foster development of novel preventive biomarkers and therapies – **KIP1, KIP3**
- **Societal impact:** Patients are empowered and better informed to be able to understand their illness and self-manage their health – **KIP4, KIP5, KIP6**
- **Economic impact:** Reduced burden of chronic inflammatory diseases worldwide that goes far beyond IBD to many other immune mediated disorders (such as diabetes, systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis, multiple sclerosis, cardiovascular diseases, among many others) – **KIP7**

4.3 Strategy to identify key exploitable results (KER)

A KER is an identified main interesting result for consortium partners and potential project external users, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to get exploited and to create impact. Expected Exploitable Results (EERs) and potential KERs will be further detailed and monitored throughout the project lifetime with the aim of broadening the perspectives on potential exploitation measures and routes. With that, tangible as well as intangible, commercially and non-commercially exploitable results will be covered. EERs have been preliminarily identified at the proposal stage and are included in the GA of the project.

At a later stage, KERs will be chosen from a list of EERs by evaluating their innovation, potential for exploitation, and impact. Collaborative efforts from both consortium partners and external stakeholders

(such as the External Advisory Board and other relevant parties) will be crucial in the development of KERs that have robust value propositions and are closely aligned with societal and commercial demands. One approach to determine and select KERs will involve conducting surveys or workshops to gather the following details for each EER:

1. What are the areas of impact or main target sectors?
2. Which problem will the project outcome solve?
3. Main project results that will be used?
4. Where will the outputs be made available during and after the project?
5. Who are the main end-users of your results?
6. How will you contact them?

The collection of this information will facilitate the creation of a list of KERs and the identification of potential routes for exploitation in relevant impact areas or target sectors. To support the development of KERs and ensure active and regular contribution from all partners in the exploitation strategy, an Exploitation Manager and KER leaders may be appointed. The KER leaders will be responsible for coordinating with all involved partners to describe and characterise specific KERs and, under the guidance of the Exploitation Manager, clarify partners' roles and legal requirements for exploitation from an Intellectual Property and IPR perspective. For each KER, an exploitation roadmap should be developed, outlining milestones, timelines, and the responsibilities of different partners for effective exploitation. Additionally, for KERs with a high level of technological readiness (TRL), business plans, Go-to-Market (G2M) strategies, or value proposition models should be developed.

The Project Management team should be kept informed of and involved in all activities related to the exploitation strategy. An IP manager from the coordinating institution (i3S) will help managing IP issues of GlycanTrigger consortium. Furthermore, strong engagement with stakeholders is critical to understanding market needs and ensuring that KERs have an impact on potential end-users.

4.4 Exploitation Measures

Exploitation activities will start from the beginning of the project and extend beyond its completion, and will require a common effort from all partners. Being the work packages with stronger scientific and technological components, WP1-WP4 will play a crucial role in supporting these activities by providing the knowledge foundation and the development of potential KERs. During these activities, different stakeholders will be targeted to ensure the maximum outcome. According to the GlycanTrigger's GA, the exploitation strategy will encompass three primary areas (Technological/Commercial Exploitation,

Research Exploitation, and Medical Exploitation) with several envisioned actions for exploitation (**Table 15**).

Table 15. GlycanTrigger exploitation actions

Technological/Commercial Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement with industry to foster the exploitation project results towards promoting healthier lifestyles; • Hosting of GlycanTrigger Transferability Workshop: targeting the medical and healthcare community, policymakers, industry and civil society, for dissemination of self-management tools and exploitable results.
Research Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of joint R&D collaboration opportunities; • Development of links and synergies with other relevant projects; • Open Access Scientific publications and conference presentations.
Medical Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting collaboration and co-creation with other initiatives and relevant stakeholders, including health care professionals and key opinion leaders; • Establishment of contacts with the medical and healthcare community; • Development of health guidelines and communication with policy makers.

4.5 Potential barriers for exploitation and mitigation strategies

The following barriers to exploitation and mitigation strategies were identified:

1. Limited involvement of patients in the policy-making process

Risk: Limited involvement of patients in policy-making process can result in policies that fail to address their concerns. This can result in lower patient satisfaction, reduced adherence to treatment plans, and decreased trust in the healthcare system. In addition, policies that do not reflect the needs and preferences of patients may not be implemented as intended, leading to decreased effectiveness and wasted resources.

Mitigation measure: Representatives from patient groups (such as EFCCA), civil society organisations, and policymakers will be actively involved through a targeted engagement strategy. Collaboration and knowledge-sharing actions will be pursued and patient input will be sought for impact assessment and policy development. GlycanTrigger will also provide and promote access to relevant resources and educational platforms.

2. Lack of citizen's trust and knowledge may limit the adoption of new therapeutic/preventive approaches and healthier choices

Risk: Limited adoption of new treatments and prevention methods can result in poorer health outcomes and increased healthcare costs. In addition, a lack of citizen's trust and knowledge may lead to scepticism and resistance to change, hindering the implementation and scaling up of innovative approaches.

Mitigation measure: Patients and citizens will be involved throughout the lifecycle of the project; research and clinical developments will be effectively communicated towards fostering access and awareness of the benefits of the proposed approach.

3. Insufficient stakeholder engagement and insufficient awareness

Risk: The stakeholders' feedback may not be incorporated into the research process, resulting in solutions that do not fully meet their needs and expectations. This can lead to a lack of support from stakeholders, hindering the implementation and adoption of new treatments and prevention methods technologies.

Mitigation measure: Specific communication tools will be developed to raise awareness and engage all the identified target groups. Efforts will be done to actively focus on the lack of input from certain groups, the multiplier programme and “attract and hold” methodology in online community management can be used to keep stakeholders interested.

4.6 Strategy for Intellectual Property Management

The management of Intellectual Property (IP) is a fundamental factor in the successful exploitation and impact maximization of the project's results, as well as to the successful and safe implementation of collaborations beyond the project without compromising all partners' best interests and the open science requirements within Horizon Europe projects. Strategies for IP management will be refined according to general EC policies within the scope of **WP6 “Project Management”, Task 6.3 “Intellectual property rights”**. The concrete outputs that will be subject to knowledge and IPR management include open-access research publications, datasets, and other knowledge products stemming from GlycanTrigger. IPR will be managed according to principles of the European Commission related to availability of the information, commercial utilization of results, confidentiality, deliverables, exploitation rights and ownership to third parties and other EU-funded projects following the disclaiming rules. The basic principle underlying herein is that results shall be the property of the partner carrying out the work leading to the results. Where several partners have jointly carried out work generating the results and where their respective share of the work is indivisible, they shall have joint ownership of such results. The partners concerned shall agree in writing the allocation, terms of exercising ownership and protection of the joint results. Distribution within the project should be free of charge, except if it is of confidential commercial nature.

Chapter 5

Final Remarks

5. Final Remarks

The Deliverable 5.1 provides the guidelines for the GlycanTrigger partners to participate in the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, and potentiate the impact of the project, as expected for Horizon Europe. The methodologies proposed herein have a strong interplay but very particular and distinct aims. The set of activities proposed herein will be monitored throughout time and required updates on this initial plan will be made to safeguard effective outreach, including under the scope of deliverables D5.2 “Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 2 “(M24), D5.3 “Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 3” (M48) and D5.4 “Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 4” (M70).

